

Quantum Free Particle//Photon Energy, Information, Force and Spacetime

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 23, 2023

The Lorentz transformation of special relativity is based on velocity. Although this velocity may be differentiated by time, the notion of force is not needed to obtain the Lorentz matrix for a particle with rest mass. In particular, in special relativity one considers frames moving at constant velocities. In the case of a photon, the Lorentz transformation preserves the form of Maxwell's electromagnetic equations. As a result, there does not seem to be a focus on force, rather the emphasis is on the two 4-vectors (p,E) and (x,t) for a particle with rest mass and photon. Nevertheless, a particle with momentum (and the capability to interact) imparts an impulse. In fact, one may think of energy changing due to an impulse (which includes force). Thus from an information point of view, one may ask: Does this force which creates a change in energy/momentum "disappear" as the particle/photon moves at constant speed only to "reappear" when it strikes a surface? If not, where is the information of this force stored? We argue it is associated with a change in energy and momentum of a free particle which in turn is linked to an internal ruler/clock i.e. the quantum frequency and wavelength from $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which preserves the force because a spatial probability distribution is created (for the wavelength). This force is linked with a direction i.e. the direction of p through the two dimensionality of $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, we argue that the force does not disappear, rather it is manifest in the internal clock and ruler which define spacetime for the free quantum particle, but in a probabilistic manner with the distribution being deterministic to ensure it maps to spatial invariance. One might at first find it surprising that force, usually associated with acceleration (i.e. deterministic motion) is now associated with probability $\cos(px)$ in space (, but deterministic probability, not random), but E,p and x,t are intertwined through the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ for both a particle with rest mass and photon, so if E and p change, it is not necessarily surprising that t,x also change. Thus an impulse may change p and E , but then remains manifest in the system through the internal clock and ruler gradations in such a way that speed is still constant on average.

Internal Clock and Ruler

If a particle moves through space at a constant speed, one may measure this speed using an external clock and ruler. A question arises: What if there is no observer with an external clock or ruler? Does there exist an internal clock and ruler? In previous notes we have argued that this is the case. Not only does a particle with rest mass or photon carry an internal clock and ruler, but these are linked to the value of energy and momentum through the Lorentz invariant:

$$S = -Et+px \quad ((1))$$

If frequency = \hbar/E and wavelength = \hbar/p , then S remains constant which is the behaviour of a Lorentz scalar which ((1)) is. Thus, as we have argued in previous notes, special relativity gives rise to the idea of frequency and wavelength.

In the case of a photon, however, this notion already exists with the wave equation:

$$\text{Velocity} = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength} \quad (2)$$

if one writes $v = x/t$ and $\text{frequency} = \hbar/E$ and $\text{wavelength} = \hbar/p$.

Notion of Force

The Lorentz matrix may be obtained for a particle with rest mass without directly using the idea of force. For example, one may consider a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$. From the point of view of someone in a frame moving at constant velocity $-v$ (no acceleration-no force), the particle is moving with velocity $v = x'/t'$. Thus there is a jump from $(x=0, t=t_0)$ to $(v t', f(v))$. This may be expressed in matrix form and if one wishes the matrix to be unitary one has:

$$\begin{vmatrix} f(v) & v f(v) \\ v f(v) & f(v) \end{vmatrix} \quad (3)$$

((3)) applies to both (x,t) and (p,E) i.e. $(0, m_0)$ ($c=1$). If one considers that the norm of a 4-vector remains constant because $(0, m_0)$ and (p, E) are equivalent in the sense that they are the same state as viewed from a rest frame and a moving one, one finds that $f(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$. It may be shown that $b=c$, the speed of light in a vacuum.

Nowhere in the above argument does the notion of force appear explicitly. We argue, however, that it is present implicitly. First of all, the rest mass m_0 , needs to be measured and this seems to require the notion of force. In particular, it moves in a certain way in a gravitational field and also has inertia so a certain amount of force is needed to accelerate it. Secondly, a particle at rest may be set into constant motion by applying an impulse (force), so the "view of the particle" from the constantly moving frame is equivalent to delivering an impulse to the particle.

As a result, we argue that from the point of view of information, information associated with a force is applied to a particle or photon in an impulse hit and the momentum and energy change. Where is the force information now? Does the notion of force disappear to be replaced by the notion of a new E, p , but then "reappear" when the particle/photon strikes a surface? In other words, is the force related information turned "on" and then "off" and then "on" again at an interaction? We try to argue that this force information may be present "all along" even for a particle moving at a constant speed as argued in (1).

The question which immediately arises is: Where is this force information stored if the particle moves at constant speed? This seems to be a reasonable question given the Newtonian view of a particle as a point which translates through spacetime, defined by an external clock and ruler, which manifests the presence of a force by accelerating. Thus, if there is no acceleration (in a one dimensional problem) there is no force. This suggests that a very different picture is needed to account for the force information and yet at the end, the particle must have constant momentum (and speed) and move in a specific direction in one dimension. This is a different view from a Newtonian one. One may ask: Where does the Newtonian view change? We

suggest that the notion of $x=vt$ must somehow break down, even though on average it still holds.

$x=vt$ is deterministic motion and one may at first think of replacing it with another type of deterministic motion which involves action-reaction forces, but still yield $x=vt$ on average. In this way there is a specific direction, deterministic action-reaction forces and yet $x=vt$ on average. Both $x=vt$ and the deterministic approach rely on infinite resolution of x and t . We suggest that the notion of an internal time and ruler break this deterministic picture and lead to a different view, a probabilistic one, which also contains force.

Creating An Internal Ruler

We argue that the idea of creating an internal ruler and clock for constant motion is key. This might at first seem unusual. For instance, all photons have the same speed c in a vacuum so one might suspect that one clock and ruler apply to all i.e. the external clock and ruler. For both a photon and particle with a rest mass, however, one has the Lorentz invariant:

$$S = -Et + px$$

In the case of the photon $S=0$, so if E and p change such that their ratio doesn't change, there is no reason why x and t may not change such that their ratio also remains fixed. Thus a change in E and p implies a change in x and t i.e. within an internal clock and ruler for a particle moving with constant p . The idea of constant p (or speed), however, suggests that all points along x are the same, but a ruler breaks this spatial invariance because there are "special" points marking the ruler gradations. Thus, if a particle or photon creates its own ruler, it seems a probability distribution in x must be created with 0 values at the gradation marks. Physically, however, there is no reason to have a probability distribution in x unless there is a force enforcing it. A symmetric probability distribution in x , however, does not indicate a direction of motion which must exist. This might suggest a skewed distribution, but this tries to combine a probability distribution with the notion of motion and leads to a skewed density which does not map to an average constant density in x implied by $x=vt$.

As a result, two symmetric probability densities may be used as two dimensions, each containing force. This yields a direction of motion, yet the modulus maps to a constant indicating that each x point has the same probability. Thus two deterministic probability distributions are used i.e.:

$$\cos(px) + i \sin(px) \quad \text{with "i" indicating a second dimension} \quad ((4))$$

As a result, force is contained in these distributions and is represented by p which is half the impulse of a particle reflecting with the same magnitude of momentum in an interaction. If an impulse interaction occurs and the momentum (and energy) change, then the distribution changes to incorporate the new "p" which is proportional to the new possible impulse. Thus force does not disappear, only to reappear. It is present all of the (external) time, but manifests itself in an unusual way, namely in creating a deterministic probability distribution. As a result, one cannot have infinite resolution suggested by $x=vt$ and still retain the force information crucial

to a particle with momentum p , yet $x=vt$ still holds on average and so the probability distribution (linked to force) is deterministic.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that even though the Lorentz matrix of special relativity may be obtained without the explicit notion of force by considering frames moving at constant relative speeds, a change in momentum may also be obtained through an impulse. Thus the notion of force is present in special relativity because an impulse in the lab frame produces a result equivalent to what a viewer in a constant moving frame sees. From an information point of view, we argue that if an impulse changes momentum (for either a particle with rest mass or a photon), this force information should still be present within the particle/photon. In particular, the particle/photon may later strike a surface and impart an impulse. Thus we suggest that force information should not be “turned on”, then “turned off” and finally “turned on” again when an impulse occurs. It should exist all of the (external) time. Newtonian mechanics suggests that the particle/photon moves as $x=vt$ and this must also hold, at least on average for an object with constant momentum. In fact, the condition seems stronger. The particle moving at constant speed, but containing forces, should somehow map to result which treats all x points the same.

Special relativity, through the Lorentz invariant $S = -Et + px$, suggests there is a frequency \hbar/E and wavelength \hbar/p which keep S constant. These values are linked to E, p and define an internal clock and ruler gradations. These, however, break invariance in time and space and so are linked with force. Thus the notion of force may remain in a particle or photon if it is linked with an internal ruler or time gradation. In the case of the ruler, this means one must have a probabilistic scenario i.e. a spatial distribution because the endpoints of the gradation “differ” from the other points. Because the gradation points differ, they must be distinguished and $x=vt$ does not distinguish. Furthermore, replacing $x=vt$ by a deterministic scheme involving positive and negative acceleration such that on average one has $x=vt$ completely changes the mechanics of the problem and violates spatial invariance which actually does exist for constant motion. How then may one have the notion of spatial invariance and still have force included? We suggest that a probability distribution is required, but this does not indicate a direction of motion unless it is skewed. It cannot be skewed, however, if it maps into spatial invariance. Thus we suggest two symmetric distributions representing two dimensions or $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$, such that the modulus does actually map into spatial invariance, yet the two distributions represent the internal ruler gradations and hence force.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco, R. Quantum Average Momentum Compared with Classical Statistical Pressure Part IV Interference in Terms of Probabilistic Impulses (preprint, zenodo, 2023)